

Bioprospecting Soil-Derived *Aspergillus fumigatus* Phytase for Enhanced Mineral Bioavailability in Animal Feed and Sustainable Agriculture

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Abstract: Phytic acid is the primary storage form of phosphorus in plant seeds and a prominent anti-nutritional factor that chelates essential divalent minerals like calcium (Ca), reducing their bioavailability in soil ecosystems and monogastric animals. Microbial phytases serve as effective biocatalysts capable of liberating these bound nutrients. This study aimed to isolate phytase-producing microorganisms from farmland soil and evaluate the enzymatic potential of a selected isolate on mineral bioavailability using both in vitro screening and an in vivo albino rat model. Rhizosphere soil samples were collected from the University of Benin and screened qualitatively and quantitatively on phytate-specific medium (PSM) supplemented with 0.5% calcium phytate. Extracellular phytase production by the most potent isolate, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, was optimized under submerged fermentation using potato dextrose broth and oat flour. For the in vivo trial, 51 baby albino rats were divided into four dietary groups and administered varying concentrations of phytic acid along with daily serialized treatments of lyophilized phytase (0.12 g/kg, 0.03 g/kg, and 0.06 g/kg) over a 33-day period. Blood, urine, stool, liver, and kidney samples were collected in 7-day cycles to track calcium accumulation. Quantitative evaluation confirmed robust extracellular phytase synthesis by *A. fumigatus* under optimized environmental parameters of 30°C and pH 3.5. The enzymatic activity effectively mediated the progressive degradation of phytate complexes. In the animal experiment, tissue analysis revealed structured, statistically significant shifts ($p < 0.05$) in calcium storage capacity across the liver, kidneys, and blood over the four-week period, directly corresponding to the administered phytase-to-phytate ratios. The findings demonstrate that soil-derived *A. fumigatus* is a highly viable, eco-friendly bioresource for producing active phytase enzymes. Its dual capability to enhance mineral dynamics in agricultural soils and systematically reverse the anti-nutritional constraints of phytic acid in vivo underscores its immense potential for animal nutrition optimization.

Keywords: *Aspergillus fumigatus*, Phytase, Calcium bioavailability, Food/Feed, Farmland soil, Anti-nutritional factors, Albino rats

1.0 Introduction

Phytic acid (myo-inositol hexakisphosphate) is the major storage form of phosphorus in cereals, legumes, and oilseed crops, accounting for nearly 90% of the total phosphorus present in plant seeds. Although it serves as an important phosphorus reserve for seed germination and plant growth, phytic acid is widely recognized as an anti-nutritional factor because it strongly chelates essential minerals such as calcium, zinc, iron, and magnesium, forming insoluble phytate complexes that reduce their bioavailability. In monogastric animals, the absence of sufficient endogenous phytase enzymes limits the digestion of phytate, resulting in poor mineral utilization and increased phosphorus excretion into the environment. Consequently, improving phytate degradation has become an important strategy for enhancing nutrient availability, animal nutrition, and environmental sustainability (Singh et al., 2013; Shah et al., 2018; Gunashree & Venkateswaran, 2018).

Microbial phytases have emerged as effective biocatalysts capable of hydrolyzing phytic acid into lower inositol phosphates and inorganic phosphate, thereby releasing bound minerals into forms readily available for biological uptake. These enzymes are

naturally produced by a wide range of soil microorganisms, particularly those inhabiting the rhizosphere, where they play a critical role in phosphorus cycling and nutrient mineralization. Beyond improving mineral bioavailability, microbial phytases contribute to sustainable agriculture by reducing dependence on inorganic phosphorus fertilizers, minimizing phosphorus pollution associated with livestock production, and improving the nutritional quality of plant-derived foods and animal feeds. Owing to these benefits, considerable research has focused on isolating and characterizing novel phytase-producing microorganisms for agricultural, environmental, and industrial applications.

In the present study, the concentrations of calcium was evaluated in albino rats treated with different lyophilized phytase concentrations incorporated into their feed for over a four-week period to assess the effectiveness of *Aspergillus fumigatus* produced phytase in enhancing mineral bioavailability. Calcium was selected because they are essential nutrients that is commonly bound within phytate and their release serves as an indicator of phytase-mediated phytate degradation. Monitoring the changes in mineral concentrations

across the different Groups provides insight into the influence of the phytase enzyme in reducing anti-nutritive phytate, nutrient cycling, and soil fertility. The results are expected to demonstrate the potential of phytase-producing microorganisms as eco-friendly bioresources for improving nutrient bioavailability, promoting sustainable soil management, and enhancing agricultural productivity through efficient phosphorus utilization (Vats & Banerjee, 2014; Thabiti et al., 2019).

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area:

Soil sample was collected in sterile polythene bag from farm top soil inside university of Benin from a depth of 2-6 cm to carry out isolation of microbial phytase producers. These soil samples were stored at 4°C in a refrigerator after the initial use for further purposes/re-use.

2.2 Isolation of Phytase Producing Fungi:

Isolation of phytase producing fungi was carried out using phytate *specific* medium (PSM). Fungal cultures were inoculated in fresh PSM medium to ensure enrichment of phytase producing fungi and incubated at 30°C, 165 rpm for 7 days. Fungal cultures

obtained through the enrichment process were inoculated in PSM agar medium containing calcium phytate (0.5%) as sole source of phosphorus. Plates were kept for incubation at 30°C for 5 days. After incubation, zone of clearing around the fungal growth on PSM agar plates were observed. The zones of clearing microbial cultures were collection and were screened for phytase production (Feyisola *et al.* 2014).

2.3 Qualitative screening of all isolates (yeast, bacteria and fungi) using agar plate assay

Qualitative screening of phytase producing isolates was carried out using plate assay procedure on phytase screening medium (PSM) (Holt *et al.*, 2004). The isolated yeast, fungi and bacterial cultures were qualitatively screened by observing a clear zone or halos around phytase producing colonies. The isolates having a clear zone around its growth on phytase screening medium agar (PSMA) plates (supplemented with 0.5% calcium phytate) were selected as phytase producers and preserved on slants for further studies. Acid producing colonies also solubilize calcium phytate. A counterstaining technique was used to identify the phytate-hydrolyzing capability of the microbes (Bae *et al.*, 1999). The plate

was flooded with 2% cobalt chloride for 5 min. After that, the solution was replaced and incubated for 5 min at 35 – 37°C with freshly prepared coloring reagent containing equal volumes of 0.42% (w/v) ammonium vanadate solution and 6.25% (w/v) aqueous ammonium molybdate solution. Culture displaying zone of clearance after removal of the chromogen were confirmed as phytase producers. These isolates were preserved on slants for further studies (Gu *et al.*, 2005).

2.4. Quantitative Screening of Phytase Producing Isolates

The *spore* inoculum was prepared from freshly grown SDA slant culture. Precisely 20 ml of sterile distilled water with Tween-80 0.01% (v/v) was added. The *spores* were gently scrapped using an inoculation sterile needle under strict aseptic conditions to fully *sporulate* agar slope culture. The *spore* suspension obtained was used as the inoculum. Viable *spores* in the fully sporulated slants were determined by the colony count method. The number of *spores* was determined in a Neubauer-Counting-Chamber and the inoculum of 1×10^6 spores/ml was used for fermentative production of phytase. One ml of *spore* suspension (2%) was used as inoculum in 50

ml production medium (Diba *et al.*, 2007, Singh & Satyanarayana, 2018).

2.5 Phytase Production Using Submerged Fermentation:

The 250ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 100 ml potato dextrose broth, oat flour and substrate sodium phytate (0.5%) as the growth medium was sterilized for 20 minutes at 121°C. After cooling, different chemical constituents were added independently and the fungal isolate (1ml containing 10^6 spores) showing the largest zone of clearance on the agar plates was selected to further quantitative screening by estimating extracellular phytase production in phytase screening broth (PMB). Erlenmeyer flasks (250 ml) containing 100 ml phytase screening broth and oat flour was inoculated with 1.0 ml of *spore* suspension from 10^6 spores/ml diluent and incubated in an orbital shaker at 200 rpm for 7 days at 30°C in triplicate. After incubation, the culture was filtered through No. 1 Whatman filter paper. Crude extract was centrifugation at 10000 rpm for 10 min in a refrigerated centrifuge. The phytase activity from the culture supernatant was determined by performing phytase assay using phytic acid as substrate (Vat *et al.*, 2014).

2.6 Physico-chemical Parameters Phytase Enzyme Production

i. Temperature:

Temperature effect on phytase production in submerged fermentation with *A. fumigatus* was studied. *A. fumigatus* was incubated at from 30°C. The optimal production temperature was measured daily using thermometer kit.

ii. pH:

The effect of pH on phytase enzyme production from *A. fumigatus* strain was studied by adjusting the media pH to 3.5 and measured with pH meter.

iii. Incubation time on phytase production:

The effect of time of fermentation on phytase production was monitored by incubating *A. fumigatus* in submerged state growth media for 7 days and daily testing the enzyme activity.

2.7 Phytase Assay

Estimation of phytase activity was done by colorimetric method using calcium phytate as substrate. The reaction mixture was prepared by adding 600 µl calcium phytate (substrate) with 150 µl of the crude enzyme and incubated at 35°C for 20 min. The enzymatic reaction was halted by addition of 750 µl of trichloroacetic acid solution in 5%

(w/v) and the liberated free orthophosphate (Pi) in the reaction was quantified by a modification of the method of Singh and Satyanarayana, (2018). A 750 µl of color reagent was added to the sample solution (750 µl) and the production of *phosphomolybdate* was measured *spectrophotometrically* at 700 nm. Standard curve prepared with inorganic phosphate (K₂HPO₄) of Aziz *et al.*, 2015 was used to compare the results. A unit of phytase is defined as the amount of enzyme that liberates 1µg inorganic phosphate,

2.8 Determination of phytase activity in samples

The sample was prepared by suspending or dissolving and diluting the accurately weighed amounts of sample in acetate buffer so that 2.0 ml of the final solution contained between 0.01 and 0.08 phytase units. The corrected absorbance (sample minus blank) was calculated for each sample preparation and the phytase standard solution. The calculated phytase activity (FTU per 2 ml) of each phytase solution was plot against the corresponding absorbance. The phytase activity in each sample preparation (FTU per 2 ml) from the curve was determined:

$$\text{Activity (FTU/g)} = \frac{\text{FTU per 2 mlx dilution}}{\text{Sample weight}}$$

3.9 Animal Experiment

The experiment was conducted using fifty-one (51) healthy baby albino rats. The animals weighed from 70 - 100 and were procured from the pharmacology department of university of Benin. The animal feed was compounded using the basic instructions for compounding growers feed for lab animal with some modifications. The rats were placed in the mesh cage under normal conditions (temperature 22-25°C) maintained for the period of thirty-three days, the first five days they were allowed to acclimatize. The animals were arbitrarily grouped into two groups and two sub group. Each group consisted of twenty animals each. The experimental design was to take three samples from each group without preference to gender after every seven days and sacrifice in four cycles.

Group A: contains the experimental animals that are fed with phytates incorporated feed twice the recommended daily dose and water. The sub group is male and female separated to avoid mating which will alter the experimental design.

Group B: contains the experimental animals that are fed with phytates incorporated feed exact the recommended daily intake and water. The sub group is male and female separated to avoid mating which will alter the experimental design.

Group C: these are the control group. The sub group is male and female separated to avoid mating. They are feed with only animal feed and drinking water.

Group D: contains the experimental animals that are fed with phytates incorporated feed half the daily recommended intake and water. The sub group is male and female separated to avoid mating which will alter the experimental design.

2.10 Preparation of feed incorporated phytase

The phytase was lyophilized and used as a daily serial treatment along with the feed used to feed the animal. The treatments were in these concentrations of 0.12g/kg for group A, 0.03g/kg for group B, group C was control and group D was treated with 0.06g/kg. The samples which include blood sample, urine sample, stool sample, kidney and liver samples were collected using the methods of Ozuola & Bafor, (2019).

2.8 Statistical Analysis

Enzyme activity data (IU/ml) was presentation as Mean \pm S.D and analyzed

using one-way ANOVA followed by T multiple comparison test at $p < 0.05$

3.0 Results and Discussion

Figure 1: Calcium concentration in the liver of albino rats used to monitor the storage ability of element (Fe) in the presence of phytase enzyme

Figure 2: Calcium concentration in the kidney of animal model used to monitor the storage ability of element (Ca) in the presence of phytase enzyme

Figure 3: Calcium concentration in the blood of animal model from week 1 to week 4

The first figure (Figure 1) shows the calcium concentration in the liver of albino rats used to monitor the storage ability of the element (Fe) in the presence of phytase enzyme. A progressive increase in calcium concentration was observed from Week 1 to Week 4 in the animal Groups. Group C consistently recorded the highest calcium values, followed by Group A, while Groups B and D generally showed comparatively lower concentrations. The increasing calcium levels may be attributed to enhanced phytate degradation by phytase-producing microorganisms, which hydrolyze phytic acid

and release bound calcium into more bioavailable forms. Phytic acid is a strong chelating agent that forms insoluble complexes with calcium, thereby reducing its availability in soil and feed. Consequently, microbial phytase activity liberates calcium from these complexes, improving nutrient availability and gut microbiome. This observation agrees with previous reports that phytase-mediated hydrolysis enhances mineral bioavailability by degrading phytate complexes (Singh et al., 2013; Shah et al., 2018). Furthermore, the gradual increase across the experimental period suggests that

gut microbial populations became more established over time, resulting in greater phytase production and more efficient mineral solubilization. These findings support the assertion that phytase-producing microorganisms play an important role in phosphorus cycling and in reducing the antinutritive phytate in feeds.

The second figure (Figure 2) illustrates the Calcium concentration in the kidney of the animal model used to monitor the storage ability of element (Ca) in the presence of phytase enzyme across the different animal Groups during the four-week study. Calcium levels were highest during Weeks 1 and 2 before declining noticeably in Weeks 3 and 4 across all Groups. This reduction may reflect increased kidney calcium bioavailability. Although phytase primarily catalyzes the hydrolysis of phytic acid to release phosphorus, enhanced bioavailability often stimulates the overall mineralization process, thereby influencing the absorption of other essential nutrients such as zinc and iron. The relatively higher calcium concentrations observed in Groups A and B compared with the other Groups further indicate that phytase influences nutrient release and gut microbial activity. Similar observations have been reported in studies showing that phytase augmentation improves micronutrient uptake in high enzymatic activity, thereby modifying nutrient dynamics in monogastric animals (Badamchi et al., 2013; Andreea et al., 2015). The observed decline in later weeks may therefore indicate active utilization of calcium during the early stage of the animal growth period, rather than in its old age.

The third figure (Figure 3) presents the calcium concentration in the blood of the animal model over the experimental period. Group B exhibited the very high calcium concentration throughout the study, whereas Group D maintained the consistent increase in values throughout the study period. Calcium directly competes with phosphorus, making its bioavailability highly dependent on phytase activity. The comparatively consistent increase in the blood calcium concentration concentrations observed in Groups within the period of study suggests more saturation of calcium in the experimental animal due to hydrolysis of phytic acid. These findings are consistent with the established role of microbial phytases in improving the bioavailability of trace minerals by degrading phytate, thereby enhancing food/feed nutrient quality and reducing the anti-nutritional effects of phytic acid (Wodzinski & Ullah, 1996; Gulati et al., 2007b; Gunashree & Venkateswaran, 2018). The results also reinforce the importance of screening monogastric animals that are fed phytase-supplemented feed for increased bioavailability of essential trace metals and microessential nutrients. And also that microbial-produced phytase enzymes are capable and efficient at phytate degradation

can improve mineral nutrition, improve animal-dung activated soil and reduce the need for inorganic fertilizer supplementation. Overall, contribute to environmentally sustainable agricultural practices

4. Conclusion

This study successfully isolated and characterized phytase-producing fungi, specifically an *Aspergillus fumigatus* strain, from farmland topsoil at the University of Benin to evaluate its potential for degrading phytic acid and enhancing mineral bioavailability. Qualitative and quantitative screening confirmed the microbe's capacity to produce extracellular phytase under optimized submerged fermentation conditions at 30°C and pH 3.5. The enzymatic activity of such rhizosphere-derived microorganisms plays a vital role in increasing the bioavailability of micronutrient-calcium, and essential trace metals that are chelated in the presence of phytate. Soil-Derived *Aspergillus fumigatus* Phytase demonstrates capacity in sustainable agriculture by liberating essential plant nutrients like calcium and zinc from insoluble phytate complexes, thereby modifying nutrient dynamics,

improving soil fertility, and offering an eco-friendly alternative to inorganic phosphorus fertilizers.

Concurrently, a 33-day in vivo experiment was conducted using 51 healthy baby albino rats divided into various dietary groups supplemented with different doses of lyophilized phytase, to monitor mineral utilization and phosphate excretion reduction in monogastric animals in the presence of lyophilized phytase treatment. Over a four-week monitoring cycle, specific physiological samples including blood, liver, and kidney tissues were collected to track changes in calcium bioavailability and storage. The resulting data demonstrated structured shifts in mineral concentrations across different Groups over time, confirming that microbial phytase interventions can systematically alter elements bioavailability and overcome the anti-nutritional effects of phytic acid in animal models.

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